

Promoting China's Soft Power: How Can China Do More?

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

China's soft power is undeniably strong. The influence of China could be felt throughout the globe. However, China's soft power is relatively weak comparing to the like of United States, France, United Kingdom or Japan. In order to strengthen her soft power, First, China should improve her image by refining its brand reputation to match with its current status as the world's major exporter. Second, China should continue to promote peaceful rise, in which China could reassure that her rise will not be a threat to the world's order and stability. Third, by advancing Chinese pop culture, China could attract more people, especially the younger population. China with her tremendous economic resource will not take much time in order to catch up and surpass other great powers in term of soft power.

Keywords: CHINA, SOFT POWER, BRAND REPUTATON, CULTURE, PEACEFUL RISE

II. Introduction

Joseph S. Nye once stated that China was far from being equal with United States in term of soft power since the former did not have the cultural industries or NGOs that the US had.¹ According to Nye, soft power was just as crucial as hard power in a sense that other states were more willing to follow its lead, if a country managed to make its power seemed legitimate, if its culture and ideology were attractive, and if it could

establish international norms consistent with its society. In the past decades, United States has been the dominated actor in spreading its soft power and led the world's order. However, the period has passed. In the contemporary era where China's economy is growing massively, China is spending billions to promote its culture, ideology, and values. To build her image, Chinese government has been spending around US\$10 billion per year on strengthening Chinese soft power to accompany its rapidly growing economic and military power. ¹At the Davos World Economic Forum, President Xi Jinping called for expanding globalization and unity in the fight against climate change, which was the summit of China's 10 years old effort to build her public diplomacy.

¹ Ibid.

China has positioned herself as a champion of globalization and economic integration, perhaps inserting an ambition to step up as a greater player in international arena. China is doing this by putting a greater effort on expanding her soft power. Beijing has been developing an international media network such as CGTV and establishing cultural study centers; namely Confucius institute, around the world. While debates discussing whether promoting China's traditions, values, language, and culture could help China to win more friends, expansive funds are backing programs to promote the country's image.²

Still, Joshua Kurlantzick, author of *Charm Offensive: How China's Soft Power Is Transforming the World*, remained suspicious of Chinese soft power. According Kurlantzick, despite the fact that Beijing has stepped up her soft power efforts since 2007, Chinese soft power appeal has not grown and has in fact declined. An *Economist* article from early 2017 also came to a similar conclusion, arguing that Chinese pop culture was nowhere as attractive or ubiquitous as American pop culture.³ Still, it is too soon to state that China fails to catch up with United State in term of soft power. Nevertheless, there are still rooms for China in order to strengthen her soft power.

II. Rebuilding Chinese brands

When it comes to brand reputation, comparing to United States, Germany or Japan, Chinese brand reputation is not well trusted. China's product quality is often questioned. Of course, China is a huge exporter and boasts a large trade surplus. China certainly produces some top-notch, world-class gadgets, especially the rising Huawei and OPPO smart phones. At the same time, examples of the terrible quality of products made in China frequently hit the news. Typically, when a mainland Chinese factory makes products under a foreign brand names, the quality is better, as brand owners specify the standards that they want must be met.⁴ However, when it comes to cheap items, China's product quality is well below the standard. China is the top producer of more than 220 industrial products. However, many of them are at the lower end of the value chain.⁵ Thus, the problem deteriorates China's image as the world's major exporter.

More importantly, as China is expanding herself as one of the world leaders through Belt and Road Initiative, infrastructure projects from the initiative are being doubtful of its quality and transparency. It is not different in Africa. Even though the Chinese are making an extensive contribution to Africa's infrastructure development, there is still a pervasive misperception that Chinese-built roads, bridges and other construction projects are of poor quality. Media reports such as "shoddy work" on power stations in Botswana or a hospital built by Chinese

² Albert E. China's Big Bet on Soft Power [Internet]. Council on Foreign Relations. Council on Foreign Relations; 2018 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/chinas-big-bet-soft-power>

³ Barker T. The Real Source of China's Soft Power [Internet]. The Diplomat. 2017 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://thediplomat.com/2017/11/the-real-source-of-chinas-soft-power/>

⁴ Tsoi R. Does "made in China" stand for cheap and of poor quality? EJINSIGHT [Internet]. EJINSIGHT. 2016 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <http://www.ejinsight.com/20160623-does-made-china-stand-cheap-poor-quality/>.

⁵ 董志成. Govt issues guidance for quality of products [Internet]. China Daily; 2017 [cited 2019Mar22]. Available from: https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/china/2017-09/14/content_31975019.htm

contractors in Angola that was closed due to cracks have come to dominate many people's realization of the quality of work performed by the Chinese company.⁶

While several campaigns under Chinese President Xi Jinping's Belt and Road are also considered the quality of the infrastructure projects, they are often overshadowed by broader concerns about the initiative, which has long been viewed as a platform to project Chinese power across the globe.⁷

According to Jonathan Hillman, senior fellow and director of the Reconnecting Asia Project at the Center for Strategic and International Studies, the Belt and Road's aspirational investment levels provided too little information, if anything, about the actual impact of new infrastructure projects. Hillman questioned about the urgency and usefulness of those projects as well as their impact on environment and climate change.⁸ Moreover, Belt and Road participants often complained of a lack of local engagement. Many Chinese-led construction endeavors were accused of importing the bulk of materials and labor from China rather than involving local companies. There were also fears of corruption for Belt and Road projects. In one instance, Chinese officials allegedly agreed to inflate the cost of infrastructure projects in Malaysia, the Wall Street Journal reported in January 2019, a claim that Xi's government had denied.

These accusations, whether they were true or not, hurt the image of China as the country is trying to strengthen her soft power and play a greater role in the global governance. It is best for China to ensure the quality of her export whether in form of low-end or high-end products, especially the quality and transparency of infrastructure investments from the BRI. If China could reassure the rest of the world that "Made in China" or China's product could be trusted, it might positively promote the image of China.

III. Promoting peaceful rise

China has been busy demonstrating that it could co-exist with the United States without the sense of rivalry that broke the two world wars. As China pursues initiatives that encourage cooperation within the area of China's responsibility, her soft power will only continue to enhance. Although in the near future, the possibility that China will become the global hegemon is unlikely, China will take her place alongside the US at the head of global governance.⁹

However, China's challenges with her neighboring countries limit China's potential in strengthening her soft

⁶ Olander E, Staden Cvan. Chinese-Built Infrastructure In Africa May Not Be As Bad As Some Think [Internet]. The Huffington Post. 2016 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: https://www.huffingtonpost.com/entry/china-infrastructure-africa_us_57b32e3ae4b0863b0284d2b3

⁷ Chandran N. Japan, not China, may be winning Asia's infrastructure investment contest [Internet]. CNBC. CNBC; 2019 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.cnbc.com/2019/01/23/belt-and-road-japan-not-china-may-be-winning-investment-contest.html>

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Du K, West J, Widmaier DW, AC THTF. Does China Have the Soft Power Necessary to Become the Global Hegemon? - AIIA [Internet]. Australian Institute of International Affairs. 2017 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/china-soft-power-hegemon/>.

power in the region and beyond. The South and East China Seas issues remain as the main obstacle for the Communist Party of China (CPC)'s efforts to present China as a humble power. The claims inculcated China's rise as a threat rather than a safeguard. Among China's neighbors, it is there that Beijing's need for soft power is the biggest, but it arguably gets the least grips from its efforts. China's surging maritime conflict with the Philippines, Vietnam, Indonesia and other parties demonstrates the limitations of its two-prong policy of simultaneously trying to build soft power and engaging in an aggressive geopolitical game. Unfortunately, this is also an area where the United States soft power is highly effective.¹⁰

Even though it has been debated that the South China Sea tensions may remain stable since China has halted land acquisition attempt to the south, the complex regional security environment may enter into a new phase of heightened tension and complexity during 2019.¹¹ This next phase could emerge as a result of China's dedicated push to secure its gains in the South China Sea via the use of military and political means alongside with sharp threats as a result of military patrols and a quantum leap in the deployment of surveillance aircraft, guided-missile destroyers, and a bank of military equipment. If the prediction happens to be true, it might insert an aggressive image of China as a threat to the regional stability.

However, If China deals with such issue peacefully, China will win trusts from her neighbors as well as other parties involved and even project herself as a peaceful rise who values peace and stability. This approach will also show the image of China as a responsible great power and convince other states to follow China's leadership in dealing with international issues. China's sincerity to peace and development is a crucial element to strengthen her soft power and overall image of China.

IV. Advancing Chinese pop culture and diversity

There is no debate that China is a country with rich and one of the oldest cultures. With more than 4,000 years of recorded history, China is one of the few existing nations which also prospered economically and culturally in the earliest stages of world civilization. Indeed, in spite of the political and social instabilities that frequently have devastated the country, China is unique among countries in her longevity and resilience as a separated politico-cultural unit. Much of China's cultural development has been achieved with relatively little outside influence.¹²

Moreover, Chinese language is also one of the most spoken languages around the world, which reflects how powerful Chinese Culture is. More people speak Chinese than any other language in the world. Nowadays,

¹⁰ China's soft power challenges [Internet]. Austrian Economics Center. 2019 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.austriancenter.com/chinas-soft-power-challenges/>

¹¹ Romaniuk SN, Burgers T. China's Next Phase of Militarization in the South China Sea [Internet]. The Diplomat. 2019 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://thediplomat.com/2019/03/chinas-next-phase-of-militarization-in-the-south-china-sea/>

¹² China [Internet]. Encyclopædia Britannica. 2021 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.britannica.com/place/China>

about twenty percent of the world's population, or over one billion people, speak some form of Chinese as their first native language. Various languages have evolved across China and these different languages are often known as dialects.

The establishment of Confucius Institutes is one of many great things that China has done in order to enhance her soft power. The Confucius Institute, which was named after the ancient Chinese philosopher Confucius, is a non-profit public institution which aims to promote Chinese language and culture in foreign countries. A total of 516 Confucius Institutes and 1,076 Confucius Classrooms have been established in 142 countries and regions, according to the Confucius Institute Headquarters. Among them, 135 Confucius Institutes were set up in 51 countries along the Belt and Road. Since the Confucius Institute was established 13 years ago, more than 7 million students have been trained worldwide and 2.1 million are currently studying.¹³

Still, comparing with American soft power, the appealing of China's culture and language is less attractive. One cannot deny the influence of American movie, music, sport and even food or coffee brands to the majority of the world. What distinguish between the two cultures is creativity and diversity. What make American movie and music so successful are because of the attractiveness, quality of its product as well as their appealing to younger population. Moreover, people find it more conveniently in accessing to American movie and music through social media platforms.

China's soft power strategy is also hindered by the centralized nature of the state. Chinese governments play a very crucial role in the accumulation of soft power, but they are limited in what they can achieve without a supportive network of non-governmental organizations, private companies and influential citizens. It comprises only the Chinese language, a state sanctioned cultural history and an official ideology that is unlikely to captivate hearts and minds.¹⁴

Therefore, in order to enhance the attractiveness of Chinese culture, it is the best for China to come up with new and creative concepts whether in form of art or ideology to keep up with the phase of global trends, especially to attract younger population to favor Chinese pop culture. China has both financial and cultural potentials in order to strengthen its pop culture domination. What China could do are to be more creative, diverse and promote quality over quantity.

V. Methodology

Qualitative method is applied in this research. This research is based on secondary data to study and evaluate relevant topic issues. The secondary data are collected from various academic books, official documents,

¹³ 代艳. Over 500 Confucius Institutes founded in 142 countries, regions [Internet]. China Daily; 2017 [cited 2019Mar20]. Available from: https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/china/2017-10/07/content_32950016.htm

¹⁴ China's soft power challenges [Internet]. Austrian Economics Center. 2019 [cited 2021May15]. Available from: <https://www.austriancenter.com/chinas-soft-power-challenges/>

websites, newspapers and academic research papers related to the topic.

VI. Conclusion

China's soft power is undeniably strong. The influence of China could be felt throughout the world. With her current status as the world's second largest economy, China has no trouble in using its financial mean to strengthen her soft power. The Chinese government, to promote China's image, has been spending billions USD every year to strengthen her soft power to accompany China's rapidly growing economic and military power. Especially through Belt and road initiative, China has raised as an exceptionally important player in international arena. However, Financial mean cannot win trust, heart and mind of other states like what soft power is aimed for. China's soft power is relatively weak comparing to the like of United States, France, United Kingdom or Japan.

In order to strengthen her soft power, China should improve her image by refining the country's brand reputation to match with her current status as the world's major exporter and infrastructure investor. Indeed, quality should be a priority for China in order to refine Chinese brands. Besides, China should also stick with and continue to promote peaceful rise, in which China could reassure that her rise will not be a threat to the world's order and stability. This is a crucial point to improve China's overall image and convince other states to follow the great power's leadership. Last but not least, China should advance Chinese pop culture in order to attract more people, especially the younger population. The pop culture is an essential element of soft power. Contemporary art, music or movie could make people easily attract and connect with one country's culture faster than the traditional one. It is not a different case for China. China needs to upgrade her pop culture by creating more creative and good quality contents, in which will expand the fan base of Chinese art.

China with her great potential in hard power, especially economy resource, will not take much time in order to catch up with and surpass other great powers in term of soft power. Moreover, with the so-called decline of the United States, China has emerged as a champion of globalization and economic integration. It is a good opportunity for China to work on her ambition and step up as a greater player in international arena. China could achieve this by putting a greater effort on expanding and strengthening her soft power.

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